

Technical Challenges in Meeting the Next Decade's Planetary Protection Requirements

John D. Rummel
Science Mission Directorate
NASA Headquarters
Washington, DC 20546 USA
202-358-0702
jrummel@hq.nasa.gov

Abstract—Protecting solar system bodies from biological contamination is of critical importance to the future success of NASA's science and exploration missions, as is protecting the Earth from the importation of life from elsewhere, if it exists. As the planned array of missions grows, the details of the data that drive future planetary protection concerns will be increasingly important. Not all locations on a solar system body will warrant the same contamination control requirements.

contamination and the accessibility of likely habitats on other worlds. Current priorities for technology development in view of the requirements for the next decade missions are discussed and developed in this paper.

For example, the picture of Mars that has emerged from the Mars Global Surveyor and Odyssey missions stands in marked contrast from that portrayed shortly after the Viking missions of the mid-1970s. The water-ice abundance at both the polar caps, and as it is inferred from hydrogen abundance in lower latitudes, is particularly intriguing, adding to a heightened consideration that Mars might support indigenous life--or could be contaminated by life brought from Earth. Elsewhere in the Solar System the potential for a liquid-water ocean within Europa, and for liquid water under the surface of other icy bodies—including Saturn's moon Titan—can highlight the problems involved with possible biological contamination that may be carried by future missions.

A particular challenge are missions carrying perennial heat sources of high capacity and longevity (e.g., Radioactive power sources) which could, by non-nominal landings or other mission operations, be introduced to close contact with water ice--potentially forming Earthlike environments that could accommodate the growth of contaminant organisms. Sample return missions from bodies that may harbor indigenous life will also require carefully contained Earth-return phases, biohazard testing, and initial science studies to be performed in a safe receiving facility.

Translating planetary protection requirements into affordable and achievable engineering solutions at both the mission and subsystem level will require that a wide array of tools be accessible to mission designers, as well as an intimate understanding of potential sources of

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1. INTRODUCTION

Biological planetary protection in solar system exploration (hereinafter referred to simply as planetary protection) is the name given to the NASA and COSPAR policy aimed at preventing biological contamination of other worlds and the potential contamination of Earth by extraterrestrial life, if any [1,2]. This policy has been applied to solar system exploration missions since their inception in the early 1960s. It is intended not only to protect the Earth from harmful contamination, but to preserve the opportunity to learn about the existence of life or significant organic chemistry elsewhere, without erasing the very information that space exploration is intended to reveal. As an endeavor to protect the Earth, the difficulties of protecting the entire populace of the Earth from a biological unknown is generally balanced against the benefit of learning about extraterrestrial worlds, and perhaps extraterrestrial life. Such a calculation involves a careful analysis of the potential of extraterrestrial life to be returned to Earth within a space-borne sample, and a conservative approach to executing sample return missions—despite the fact that extraterrestrial life cannot be proven to exist.

Conversely, the potential contamination of other worlds is largely governed by the presence of extraterrestrial Earth-like environments that may be colonized by microbes carried by space missions. There is no question that life exists here—and Earth microbes are proving to be much more robust survivors than once was believed. Increasingly, there is evidence that Earth-like environments on other planets also exist. This combination of facts makes the recent astrobiological exploration of the solar system an enticing proposition, and calls for careful attention to biological contamination issues in pursuing missions to bodies such as Mars and Europa that have evidence of potentially available liquid water, and other factors that may allow for the presence of life—including indigenous life—to exist there.

Despite general agreement about the importance of planetary protection measures, there tends also to be a general resistance to fully implementing such measures.

This is not surprising, since the implementation of planetary protection measures can be both expensive and difficult. Nonetheless, on missions to planets or small bodies that may be of importance to chemical evolution and the origin of life, the implementation of stringent measures may be necessary. This is particularly the case for Mars or Europa—or for sample return missions from those or other, similar, targets

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of interest. In such cases, increasing levels of technological readiness may offer solutions that will enable projects to avoid biological contamination, while lessening the implementation and operational burdens associated with such measures.

In view of discussions provided elsewhere about planetary protection for Mars [3], this paper will focus on missions to planetary environments largely beyond Mars orbit, and in particular missions to those small bodies where the presence of liquid water at one time or another has provided for the tempting whisper of possible organics, water, and perhaps life itself. Increasingly, and surprisingly, it appears that such bodies may be widespread in the outer solar system [cf., 4].

Table 1. Required Planetary Protection Technologies

Mission Aspect	Required Technology	Targeted Applications
Prelaunch/Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cleaning to sterility • Assays for rapid assessment of cleanliness (cultivable, non-cultivable, molecular) • Particle transport models • Development of orbital debris analysis code • Aseptic assembly systems • H₂O₂ and/or radiation sterilization of assembled subsystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mars missions • Europa orbiters/landers • Other icy moons orbiters/landers
Launched Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightweight biobarriers for forward contamination prevention • <i>In situ</i> sterilization systems • Container sealing systems • Mechanism or series of mechanisms for “break-the-chain” of contact • Earth targeting improvements • Earth entry vehicle for assured containment • Meteoroid protection on spacecraft 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mars missions • Europa orbiters/landers/subsurface probes • Other icy moons orbiters/landers • “Restricted Earth return” sample missions
Sample Handling Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-directional containment systems for sample handling • Systems for analysis of contained samples (Sample Receiving Facility) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mars missions • “Restricted Earth return” sample missions
Research Required to Inform the Development of Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental biology of survivability (microbial characterization in flight h/w manufacturing environments) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mars missions (inc. human missions) • Europa orbiters/landers/subsurface probes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced spacecraft designs to provide for sterilization, aseptic assembly, late RPS installation • Materials screening to enable system/subsystem sterilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Titan probes/landers/subsurface investigations • “Restricted Earth return” sample missions
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2. Missions Being Considered

In addition to the variety of Mars missions under consideration in NASA’s solar system exploration portfolio (including human missions), a variety of other robotic mission opportunities are covered by NASA’s planetary protection policy [cf., 5] and have recently been outlined by the National Research Council’s Space Studies Board the first decadal report on a strategy for the future of solar system exploration within NASA [6]. This report is a compendium of different mission possibilities ranked by priority, and including a major mission cited as the Europa Geophysical Orbiter, and a suite of smaller missions, such as Principal-Investigator-led missions of the Discovery Program and the larger, PI-led missions in the New Frontiers class (~\$700M)—including a mission to Pluto and the Kuiper Belt (now New Horizons), a mission to the poles

of Jupiter, a Comet Nucleus Sample Return, and a sample-return mission to the south polar region of the Earth’s Moon. Within the list of missions proposed by the NRC and those already underway in NASA’s robotic exploration program, there is ample opportunity to illustrate planetary protection implementation concepts and the required technology. In this regard, we can consider the requirements of a new mission to the Galilean satellites of Jupiter—the Jupiter Icy Moons Orbiter (JIMO), of Stardust, a mission to return a sample from a comet, and of Dawn, a mission to visit two major asteroids, Vesta and Ceres.

The Dawn mission is typical in some respects of a mission that is not intending to land on any body that might sustain life. Although the asteroids Vesta and Ceres may themselves be important to the story of life’s origins, neither has been considered traditionally to be a likely life-site—rather they have been of interest to the story of the chemical

Figure 1 - The Jupiter Icy Moons Orbiter (JIMO) is an example of a mission requiring innovative implementation and technologies for planetary protection compliance (artist’s conception credit JPL/NASA).

evolution of the solar system. Therefore, except for two particular issues, Dawn would be a mission that would only be required to document its operational characteristics, trajectories, and plans. The first issue is that Dawn is also planning to use a flyby of Mars to assist it in its trajectory for its first asteroidal rendezvous with Vesta. Accordingly, Dawn must take on a few of the additional planetary protection requirements that are imposed to ensure that it doesn't inadvertently impact Mars. The second issue with the mission is of a more prospective nature—and has to do with one of the primary targets of Dawn: Ceres. Recent observations and theoretical considerations (McCord, personal communications) have suggested that Ceres may conceal a high proportion of ammonia beneath its icy exterior, allowing for the potential of liquid water existing within its deep subsurface. If this proves to be the case—and if the data provided by the mission when it reaches Ceres are consistent with these astronomical observations—Dawn operations and its end-of-mission scenario would have to accommodate a firm requirement to avoid contact with Ceres. Such a requirement would be imposed to avoid possible biological contamination of such a body of water, although its existence could not be determined if the mission did not go there in the first place.

JIMO, on the other hand, faces an issue that is already partially decided—it is widely believed that at least one and very likely all of Jupiter's icy moons conceal liquid water beneath their surface ice. In the case of Europa, it was previously determined that the Galileo spacecraft should be plunged into Jupiter rather than endangering that ocean with possible biological contamination. Based on the implications of recommendations provided to NASA by the National Research Council [7], it is anticipated that JIMO will either completely avoid contact (at some level of rigor) with Europa and the other icy moons—or that it will be so clean (substantially free of microbial life) that contact will not result in biological contamination. This latter approach may be aided by the challenging radiation environment in the jovian system, but since the spacecraft will be at least partially shielded from radiation effects, the natural environment alone will not be sufficient to make JIMO planetary-protection friendly, in and around Europa in particular.

Stardust is a mission that has recently completed a comet dust collection pass in January 2004, and which will return to Earth in January of 2015. Like Genesis, the recently returned mission from the Earth-Sun L-1 point, Stardust has been classified as an “unrestricted Earth return” mission for planetary protection purposes, using decision criteria provided by the National Research Council in 1998 [8]. For Stardust, the most compelling consideration is that the Earth is regularly bombarded by comet dust particles, to the tune of about 40,000 tons per year. The natural flux of material

far outweighs the amount that the mission could return, although the known source of the particles captured, and the potential for a near-pristine collection of that dust, argues strongly for the value of the Stardust mission. With an “unrestricted Earth return” classification, the most important safety criterion for the Stardust return mission is precise targeting. With good navigation, even a parachute failure on landing does not have to endanger the Earth, its biosphere, or any of its inhabitants. That would not be the entire consideration with the return of a sample from someplace like Europa, which might harbor its own inhabitants.

3. TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPLEMENTATION

Table 1 lists a suite of planetary-protection-related technologies and their application. It is obvious from the table that a planet like Mars—both relatively easy to reach, and which may possess liquid water and possibly life—provides a variety of challenges that may require the entire gamut of these technologies. For other missions under study by NASA, such technologies may or may not be considered necessary.

For example, the aforementioned Dawn mission can be operated in a fashion similar to that of Galileo, with a “wait and see” provision in mind. In Dawn's case, operational constraints (and the very light pull of Ceres) substitute for technological solutions.

A Europa orbiter like JIMO is not so lucky. Energetically, it may be impossible to avoid an eventual crash of the spacecraft into the European surface. In such a case, it is currently not known how long it would take for microbes landing on (or under) the surface of Europa to reach a subsurface ocean—and it may be that that time is fairly short, by geological and even biological standards. Hence, the spacecraft will have to avoid taking live microbes to the European surface.

If one can envision that the large, exposed portions of the spacecraft can depend on the harsh radiation environment of Europa to quickly eliminate most Earth microbes (one form of *in situ* sterilization), and to somewhat-less-quickly eliminate radiation-resistant microbes like the bacterium, *Deinococcus radiodurans*, then the problem is less one of the quantity of spacecraft that needs to avoid contaminating Europa, and one of the biological qualities of that portion of the spacecraft that is shielded from radiation. On those portions of the spacecraft, a combination of cleaning-to-sterility and something like hydrogen peroxide or radiation sterilization—or dry heat microbial reduction—may be used in conjunction with aseptic assembly to ensure the cleanliness and microbial inertness of the non-shielded

components. Likewise, particle transport models may establish the need to shield the clean portions of the spacecraft, at least temporarily, from those portions that have not yet met with European radiation. The duration of the segment of the mission that may require such recontamination prevention will, of course, depend on the fundamental survival characteristics of the non-removed Earth organisms exposed to that same environment.

While Stardust is largely dependent on navigation for sample-return safety, missions that may wish to return a sample from an extraterrestrial body with liquid water, metabolic energy sources, carbon chemistry, and protection from radiation will also need to contain that sample to a high degree of reliability. There are a variety of targets in the outer solar system that might share the distinction (with Mars, see [3]) of requiring a mission classified as “restricted Earth return” from a planetary protection perspective. A sample return from Europa (even if the sample were collected from material blasted into European orbit, as has been proposed), or from the surface or sub-surface of a body like Ceres, would be examples that could fall into that classification.

If so, the requirements for containment throughout the Earth return phase of the mission, and until samples are delivered to a receiving facility, would be quite stringent—with a containment failure probability required to be approximately at the 1 in 10^6 level. Attaining such a containment assurance level would require advanced container sealing techniques, mechanisms to avoid returning uncontained material, a robust Earth-entry vehicle, and sufficient navigation accuracy and micrometeoroid protection to ensure that once the Earth-entry vehicle is irretrievably targeted to Earth, it will be capable of landing safely and in the correct location.

Further issues will arise when such samples are eventually removed from their containers. It is true that systems are needed to properly contain and analyze returned dust, rock, and atmospheric samples from a place like Mars—although such materials have ready analogs in the form of terrestrial or lunar materials familiar to sample scientists. It will be quite another thing to develop the same sort of capabilities for extraterrestrial liquid samples—which may be corrosive or volatile—or for ice and gas samples that must be analyzed under conditions incompatible with the human researchers doing the work.

4. SUMMARY

In addition to the technologies required to successfully implement planetary protection in Mars exploration, there are a number of missions to small bodies and other targets

in the outer planets that can also be envisioned to require similar solutions. As to these missions, the class of opportunities reflected in NASA’s New Frontiers program, as well as the larger-scale missions of the scope of Cassini, or even JIMO, will provide ample challenges when coupled with complex and compelling environments that may, indeed, hide the secrets of life in our solar system. Only by approaching these sites with caution and care can we unlock their clues—and potentially find that life may have developed elsewhere in this solar system.

Accordingly, an investment in planetary protection technology to support future missions beyond Mars orbit is well-warranted. Such an investment can be largely complementary to the specific technology solutions that will enable future exploration of the non-icy surface areas of Mars—and that one day may allow exploration into those areas of Mars, such as its polar caps and subsurface, that most closely resemble exploration targets among the outer planets. Today, while we are only beginning to scratch the surface of outer planet satellites and have yet to view a Kuiper-belt object close-up, we have an opportunity to provide for the technology that can enable exciting future discoveries, and fully capable missions to make them.

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BIOGRAPHY

John Rummel is the NASA Planetary Protection Officer. He has undertaken multiple assignments for NASA, separated by four years as Director of Research and Education at the Marine Biological Laboratory in Woods Hole, Massachusetts. His B.A. is from the University of Colorado, and his Ph.D. in Biological Sciences from Stanford.